

ISic1048

I.Sicily inscription 1048

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140527

1. [—]υσις *ho* Χιμ-
2. άρου ²⁷[Λ]ϋσις *ho* Τιμ | άδου? (Jeffery, LSAG)²⁷.
- 3.

Edition: PHI175431

1. [Λ]ϋσις *ho* Τιμ-
2. άδου.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492676

EDCS 39102202

EDCS 64900731

PHI 140527

PHI 175431

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0227 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 45.1351bis
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 12.0408
- Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 107 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5458
- Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensa. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.20
- Arena, R. 1998. Iscrizioni greche arcaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. V. Iscrizioni di Taranto, Locri Epizefiri, Velia e Siracusa. Alessandria. At no.76

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1048. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385398>